

A Statistical Assessment of the Likelihood of Post-Harvest Losses Among Tuberculosis-Affected Farmers in Benue State

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a critical public health issue, particularly in countries with limited economic resources, and has significant implications for agricultural productivity. This study statistically assessed the likelihood of post-harvest losses among tuberculosis-affected farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. Utilizing a cross-sectional design, data were collected from 300 TB-affected farmers across Agatu, Gwer West, and Katsina-Ala Local Government Areas through structured questionnaires. Specifically, it assessed how TB affects the timeliness of harvest and the likelihood of experiencing post-harvest losses. The study employed descriptive statistics, Chi-Square test of independence, and binary logistic regression analysis to explore the relationship between TB and post-harvest losses. Chi-square test of independence revealed that, tuberculosis significantly hinders farmers' ability to harvest at the appropriate period, leading to increased post-harvest losses ($\chi^2 = 100.5$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.000$). The symmetric measures (Phi = 0.579; Cramer's V = 0.579) indicated a moderately strong association between TB and post-harvest losses. Logistic regression results further showed that period of harvest ($\text{Exp}(B) = 12.239$), inappropriate harvest losses ($\text{Exp}(B) = 4.828$), decline in income ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.500$), and feeling after harvest ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.702$) were significant predictors of post-harvest losses (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.517$; classification accuracy = 83%). The study concludes that TB, particularly when coinciding with harvest periods, significantly increases the risk of post-harvest losses among affected farmers due to physical debilitation and labour shortages. It recommends health interventions should be aligned with the agricultural support programs to ensure TB-affected farmers receive medical and physical assistance during harvest periods.

KEYWORDS: Tuberculosis, logistic regression, chi square test of independence, post-harvest losses, TB-affected farmers

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) counts as a highly contagious infection brought on by the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, a pathogen that predominantly affects the lungs but can also invade organs such as the spine, kidneys, and brain under advanced conditions (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). The causative organism of TB, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, grows slowly and can remain latent in human tissues for extended periods before progressing to active infection, especially when the immune system becomes compromised (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). Transmission occurs through inhalation of droplets from coughing, sneezing, or speaking by infected persons (Center for Disease and Control [CDC], 2022). Although exposure does not always result in active disease, latent infections may progress under immunosuppression (Horsburgh *et al.*, 2015).

Globally, TB remains a major public health challenge. WHO (2024) reported an estimated 10.8 million new cases and 1.25 million deaths in 2023, with its effects felt most acutely in countries with limited economic resources. The disease imposes severe socioeconomic burdens, especially on rural farming communities where labour capacity is essential for livelihood and productivity (Abah *et al.*, 2020; Luciano & Roess, 2020).

In Nigeria, TB prevalence continues to affect agricultural communities disproportionately, where farmers rely heavily on physical labour for production and post-harvest activities (Oluwatayo & Adedeji, 2019). The illness weakens physical strength, limits daily work ability, and creates financial strain related to treatment, reduced income, and labour shortages (Abah *et al.*, 2020). These conditions may significantly delay harvest operations, an important factor known to drive post-harvest losses when not executed promptly (FAO, 2019; Kumar & Kalita, 2017).

Although literature has extensively documented the socioeconomic effects of TB, there is limited research examining post-harvest losses specifically among TB-affected farmers. This study addresses that gap by statistically assessing the likelihood of post-harvest losses among tuberculosis-affected farmers in Benue State using Chi-Square and binary logistic regression models (Tanimura *et al.*, 2014; WHO, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a cross-sectional survey design to assess whether TB affects farmers' ability to harvest at the appropriate period and the resulting likelihood of post-harvest losses. This design enabled systematic collection of data from diverse TB-affected farmers across selected LGAs in Benue State.

Population and Sample

The population comprised farmers diagnosed with TB who actively engage in farming and post-harvest activities.

A sample of 300 TB-affected farmers was drawn from Agatu, Gwer West, and Katsina-Ala using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across gender, age, education, and farming experience.

Data Collection Instrument

A structured questionnaire consisting of four sections—Demographics, Health Status, Farming Practices, and Support Systems—was administered to respondents. The instrument captured TB effects, harvesting behaviour, labour availability, and post-harvest loss experiences.

Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable: The dependent variable is post-harvest losses and was measured as binary derived variable from the questionnaire. Respondents were asked whether they experience post-harvest losses due to TB, coded 1 for YES, there is reported significant post-harvest losses due to TB, and coded 0 for NO, there is no reported post-harvest losses due to TB.

Independent Variables: Age, gender, education, farming experience, year diagnosed, harvest method, period of harvest, decline in income, inappropriate harvest losses, comfort after harvest, and health effect of TB.

Data Processing and Analysis

Data were coded and entered into SPSS.

The analysis involved, descriptive statistics, chi square test of independence and binary logistic regression.

Chi-Square Test of Independence to test association between TB and inappropriate harvest timing.

Chi-Square (χ^2) test of independence examines whether two categorical variables are statistically related (Agresti, 2018; Field, 2017). The equation for Chi-Square (χ^2) test of independence is given below;

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

where;

O_{ij} is observed frequency in the i th row and j th column

E_{ij} is expected frequency, computed as

$$E_{ij} = \frac{(\text{Row Total}_i)(\text{column Total}_j)}{\text{Grand Total}}$$

r is number of rows

c is number of columns

The calculated Chi-Square (χ^2) test of independence value is compared with the critical value from the Chi-square distribution table at a given significance level usually $\alpha = 0.05$ and appropriate degrees of freedom ($df = (r - 1)(c - 1)$). If $p \leq 0.05$, there is a significant association between the two categorical variables; otherwise, there is no significant association (Agresti, 2018).

Binary Logistic Regression to predict likelihood of post-harvest losses

In the statistical analysis of the effects of tuberculosis (TB) on post-harvest losses, a binary logistic regression model was used to assess the likelihood of experiencing significant post-harvest losses based on a farmer's TB status and other related factors. Since the dependent variable (post-harvest loss due to tuberculosis) was categorized into two distinct outcomes, YES or NO, the logistic regression model was a preference choice for analysis.

Binary logistic regression is a statistical method used for modelling the relationship between a binary dependent variable and one or more independent variables. The dependent variable takes only two possible outcomes, typically coded as 0 and 1, representing categories such as success/failure, presence/absence, or affected/unaffected. The model estimates the probability of an event occurring by applying the logistic function to a linear combination of independent variables (Hosmer, Lemeshow & Sturdivant, 2013).

A binary choice of the i th individual is represented by a random variable y_i that takes on the value of 0 if a farmer did not experience postharvest losses of crops due to inappropriate harvest period as a result of TB and 1 if the farmer experiences postharvest losses of crops due to inappropriate harvest period as a result of TB. Where p_i is the probability that y_i takes on the value 1, and then $1 - p_i$ is the probability that that y_i is 0. This can be written using the probability function for y_i as

$$F(y_i) = p_i^{y_i}(1 - p_i)^{1-y_i}, \quad y_i = 0, 1 \tag{2}$$

and

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{with probability } p \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - p \end{cases}$$

In this case, $y = 1$ when the respondent experience postharvest losses of crops due to inappropriate harvest period as a result of TB and $y = 0$ when the respondent did not experience postharvest losses of crops due to inappropriate harvest period as a result of TB.

A logistic regression model is presented below. Linear probability models are constrained between 0 and 1, whereas linear functions are inherently unbounded. Therefore, to ensure the probability is no longer restricted, a transformation is necessary (Allison, 2012). As noted by Allison (2012), converting probability into an odds ratio eliminates the upper bound, while applying the logarithm to the odds removes the lower bound. For k explanatory variables and $i = 1, \dots, T$ individuals, the logistic model is given as:

$$\log \left[\frac{p_i}{1 - p_i} \right] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} \tag{3}$$

where p_i is the probability that y_i takes on the value 1, and then $1 - p_i$ is the probability that that y_i is 0. Solving the logit equation for p_i , we have

$$p_i = \frac{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})} \quad (4)$$

Exp (x) is the exponential function, equal to e^x , where e is the exponential constant equivalent to 2.71828 (Allison, 2012). Using the property, $\log(e^x) = x$, we can further simplify the last equation:

$$p_i = \frac{1}{(1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}))} \quad (5)$$

Generally, the outcome in multiple logistic regression analysis is often coded as 0 or 1, where 1 indicates that the outcome of interest is present, and 0 indicates that the outcome of interest is absent. If we define p as the probability that the outcome is 1, the multiple logistic regression model can be written as follows:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})}{(1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}))} \quad (6)$$

where p_i is the expected probability that the outcome is present; x_1 through x_k are distinct independent variables; and β_0 through β_k are the regression coefficients.

For this study the model is;

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Age} + \beta_2 \text{Gender} + \beta_3 \text{Education Level} + \beta_4 \text{Farming Experience} + \beta_5 \text{Year Diagnosed} + \beta_6 \text{Harvest Method} + \beta_7 \text{Period of harvest} \quad (7)$$

p is the probability of experiencing post-harvest losses due to TB

β_0 is the intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_7$ are the coefficients for each independent variable.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic distribution of the respondents. The data reveal the age, gender, education level, and year of TB diagnosis of the farmers in the study area. The data show a wide range of demographic representation across the sample of 300 TB-affected farmers. Most respondents (28.7%) were aged between 31 and 40 years, implying that tuberculosis predominantly affects economically active farmers. Males formed 54.7% of the sample, slightly higher than females (45.3%). Educational attainment was relatively high, with 40.7% having secondary education and 29.7% tertiary education. The majority (46.3%) were diagnosed with TB between 2020 and 2022, showing a recent surge in reported cases.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	15–20 years	18	6.0
	21–30 years	76	25.3
	31–40 years	86	28.7
	41–50 years	52	17.3
	51 years and above	68	22.7
Gender	Male	164	54.7
	Female	136	45.3
Education Level	No formal education	17	5.7
	Primary	72	24.0
	Secondary	122	40.7
	Tertiary	89	29.7
Year Diagnosed of TB	2013–2016	33	11.0
	2017–2019	85	28.3
	2020–2022	139	46.3
	2023–2024	43	14.3

Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Table 2 summarizes the main TB-related agricultural variables and their frequencies. A large proportion (61.3%) of respondents indicated that TB hindered them from harvesting at the appropriate period, and 63.7% experienced post-harvest losses due to TB. The predominance of self-harvesting (41%) shows high dependence on personal labour, while 55% reported income decline due to TB, indicating reduced capacity to hire assistance.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of TB-Related Farming Variables

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Harvesting Method	Self-harvesting	123	41.0
	Hired labour	101	33.7
	Assistance from relatives	76	25.3
Decline in Income due to TB	Yes	165	55.0
	No	135	45.0
Farming Experience	Less than 1 year	30	10.0
	1–6 years	91	30.3
	6–10 years	76	25.3
	11–20 years	49	16.3
	More than 20 years	54	18.0
Effects of TB on Health	No impact	40	13.3
	Minor impact	36	12.0
	Moderate impact	76	25.3
	Significant impact	66	22.0
TB Hindering Appropriate Harvest Period	Yes	184	61.3
	No	116	38.7
	Yes	191	63.7
	No	109	36.3

Chi-Square Test of Independence

The Chi-Square test of independence was used to investigate the relationship between TB hindering appropriate harvest period and post-harvest losses among affected farmers. The Pearson Chi-Square test ($\chi^2 = 100.5$, $df = 1$, $p = .000$) indicates a statistically significant relationship between TB hindering harvesting at the appropriate period and the occurrence of post-harvest losses. The strength of association, measured by Phi (0.579) and Cramer’s V (0.579), shows a moderately strong relationship, suggesting that TB’s interference with harvest timing is a key determinant of losses. This implies that TB-related delays in harvesting substantially increase the likelihood of post-harvest losses among farmers (Tanimura *et al.*, 2014; Abah *et al.*, 2020). Table 3 summarizes the output for the relationship between TB hindering appropriate harvest period and post-harvest losses among affected farmers using chi-square test of independence.

Table 3: Chi-Square Test of Independence between TB Hindering Harvest Period and Post-Harvest Losses

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	100.5	1	0.000
Continuity Correction	97.99	1	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	102.55	1	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	100.17	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	300		
Phi	0.579		
Cramer’s V	0.579		

Binary Logistic Regression Analysis

A Binary logistic regression was conducted to assess the likelihood of post-harvest losses among tuberculosis-affected farmers, using variables such as age, gender, education, year diagnosed, harvesting method, income decline, experience, health effects of TB, feeling after harvest, period of harvest, and inappropriate harvest losses. The model fit statistics are presented in Table 4. The model significantly predicts the likelihood of post-harvest losses ($\chi^2 = 141.47$, $p < .001$). The Nagelkerke R^2 value (.517) suggests that 51.7% of the variation in post-harvest losses among TB-affected farmers is explained by the included predictors. The model correctly classifies 83% of the cases, indicating strong predictive validity.

Table 4: Model Fit and Classification

Test	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation
Omnibus Test of Model Coefficients	$\chi^2 = 141.47$ (df = 11)	.000	Model fits better than null model
-2 Log Likelihood	248.22		Good model fit
Cox & Snell R^2	.376		Moderate explanatory power
Nagelkerke R^2	.517		Model explains 51.7% of variance
Classification Accuracy	83.0%		High predictive ability

Table 5: Binary Logistic Regression Coefficients and Odds Ratios

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Decline in Income	-.693	.346	4.019	.045	.500
Farming Experience	.263	.132	3.957	.047	1.301
Feeling After Harvest	-.353	.148	5.693	.017	.702
Period of Harvest	2.505	.342	53.643	.000	12.239
Inappropriate Harvest Losses	1.574	.337	21.858	.000	4.828

Results from table 5 above indicate that the period of harvest and inappropriate harvest losses are the most significant predictors of post-harvest losses. Farmers whose TB condition caused delayed harvesting were twelve times more likely to experience losses ($\text{Exp}(B) = 12.239$, $p < .001$). Income decline and comfort level after harvest were also significant, aligning with Abah et al. (2020), who noted that health-induced financial strain increases agricultural losses.

Discussion of Findings

The findings confirm that tuberculosis significantly affects post-harvest outcomes through indirect pathways such as delayed harvesting, reduced labour capacity, and income decline. Specifically, TB's interference with the appropriate harvesting period was found to significantly contribute to post-harvest losses, consistent with the first research objective. The Chi-Square test confirmed this association ($p < .001$), highlighting TB-induced physical weakness and reduced labour availability as key contributors to delayed harvesting.

The binary logistic regression model further established that the timing of harvest and the presence of inappropriate harvesting periods were the most influential predictors of post-harvest losses. Farmers who reported delayed or poorly timed harvests due to TB were over twelve times more likely to experience post-harvest losses compared to those unaffected. This supports earlier research by of Tanimura et al. (2014) and Abah et al. (2020), who emphasized that TB indirectly reduces agricultural productivity by limiting labour capacity and delaying farm operations.

Summary and Conclusion

Summary of Findings

The study assessed the likelihood of post-harvest losses among TB-affected farmers in Benue State. Descriptive analysis showed that a majority (63.7%) experienced post-harvest losses linked

to TB. The Chi-Square test confirmed a significant relationship ($\chi^2 = 100.5$, $p < .001$) between TB hindering harvest and post-harvest losses. Binary logistic regression indicated that inappropriate harvest timing ($\text{Exp}(B) = 12.239$, $p < .001$) and related losses ($\text{Exp}(B) = 4.828$, $p < .001$) were the strongest predictors. Other significant predictors included decline in income ($p = .045$) and comfort level after harvest ($p = .017$). The model explained 51.7% of the variance and correctly classified 83% of cases, confirming its robustness.

Conclusion

Tuberculosis has a substantial indirect effect on post-harvest losses among farmers in Benue State. The results confirm that TB reduces farmers' capacity to harvest on time, limits physical ability, and reduces income. These constraints lead to delayed harvesting, poor handling, and increased spoilage, culminating in greater post-harvest losses. Therefore, addressing TB in rural farming communities is crucial not only for public health but also for improving agricultural productivity and food security.

Recommendations

Since delayed or inappropriate harvesting period was found to significantly increase post-harvest losses among TB- affected farmers, health interventions should be aligned with the agricultural support programs to ensure farmers receive medical and physical assistance during harvest periods.

Supportive financial policies should be implemented to help affected farmers stabilize income levels during illness and recovery, enabling them to hire labour or adopt improved harvesting methods.

Further research should investigate the influence of other health conditions, climatic factors, and socio-economic variables on post-harvest losses. Expanding the scope to include non-TB-affected farmers and longitudinal data could provide a more comprehensive understanding of health-agriculture interactions in Benue State and beyond.

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